

Corrections

- p. 24: Definition 3.1.1 item (iii)(b) should read "... or $(y', y) \in \mathcal{R}$."
- p. 109: In equation (8.5) the vertical arrows $\downarrow \uparrow$ should read $\uparrow \downarrow$.
- p. 178: In Example 10.6.18 the references should be to network (10.22), not (10.23).
- p. 180: In Lemma 10.6.24 " $\alpha^* =$ " should be replaced by " $\alpha^*_{y \rightarrow y'} =$ ".
- p. 190: Below equation (10.39) the text should read "... $\ell = 3$, and $\ell = 3$, so ...".
- p. 266: The caption in Figure 12.13 should read "... in a $c_{AS} - c_{AB} - c_{B2S}$ projection".
- p. 276: On the right side of (13.11) replace f with μ .